

BRAVE: An Open-Source 3D Visualization Application for Breast Reconstruction and Augmentation Surgery Simulation

November 10, 2025

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1 Overview

1.1 What problem do we solve

Due to today's advancement in medical technology people are able to augment their bodies in order to fix parts of their look. We have methods to augment breast,nose,hips,remove fat from the stomach and other parts of the body. With this technology women that have survived breast cancer can therefore also use it to augment their breasts. This is popular since many women might not feel well about their look,however it would be nice if they can see the change and the effect this surgery would have on their body before actually making the final decision. This is the problem that our application is solving. It helps the patient to view how their body will look after the surgery, this implicitly also benefits the workflow between the patient, consultant, and doctor, since they can all sit and discuss the final look that the women wants to achieve. This application could be used in any clinic to help in the consultation phase. Technology like this exists already, however it is highly expensive and not every clinic can afford it, we try to fix this by offering our solution as a free application, this means that we can reach wider variety of people and crucially help more people in their recovery journey. Although an early prototype this technology could be expanded outside the field of breast augmentation into the field of general plastic surgery.

1.2 How is it going to be achieved

The goal of the project is to create an open source application for visualization of the female body for patients with breast cancer. The application should handle fine grained deformations in the breast area. The application should be developed to support multiple mobile platforms i.e: IOS and An-droid and handle different screen sizes, for example: mobile and tablet. In order to solve the problem multiple solutions will be involved. The main ones are:

- Developing intuitive UI/UX through which the client can interact with the application and apply modifications to the model. Every application that wants to target non-technical people has to have easy to understand and use interface. As one of the more famous quotes about UI/UX design says: "If you have to explain it then it's not good". A good user interface does not need tutorials,or explanation the user has

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intuitive sense of what each button,icon, and control does. This makes the application feel smooth and easy to use.

- Use an highly sophisticated graphics library (game engine) to apply the modifications to the model. Since we have to deal with 3D graphics, it only makes sense to use a game engine. These technologies are built for this specific use case. Our case falls into the category of simulation, these engines can offer massive performance in this scenario, while offering us all the necessary tools to build the solution, like: animation system, input system, multiple platform support,3D rendering, etc.

- Use a modeling library to create the 3D model of the female body and integrate it into the solution. Since we need high fidelity model of the female body we will need to use something like: Maya or Blender in order to either create the model from scratch or import an open source one and modify it to fit our needs. We will most likely choose the latter option.

- Develop a pipeline for development and allow for easy distribution of the software for the targeted platforms. We will strictly adhere to the principles of CI/CD so that we can easily develop the code across multiple people and also deploy the code to the targeted platforms.

- Perform complex mathematical models on the 3D model that would allow for proper deformation and achieve a look and feel which is as close to reality as possible.

2 Intended Audience

As stated above the intended audience is mainly clinics that would use this software to support patients in their recovery journey. The

software should be developed with the audience in mind and have a professional and medical approach to it. This document is meant to be viewed by University of Groningen lecturers, supervisors, and people that would like to get a deeper understanding of the system or become potential contributors.

3 Architecture

In this section, I will explain the overall architecture of the project along with important design decisions regarding the technologies involved and why

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I believe they were the right fit for the project. There would also be extensive documentation on how the project could be further expanded and how to navigate what has been already done. Some of the terms used will be provided below with their respective meaning. These are important since the main solution revolves around them:

- **Static Mesh** - A static mesh is a 3D object, for example a cube. The mesh is the representation of the object, this involves the shape, vertices, edges, the texture, and materials applied to the mesh. As you

Figure 1: Static Mesh Example

can see this boulder is a static mesh. Static being that it cannot be controlled by a player and will not move, it has some geometric form, material and lighting applied to it.

- **Skeletal Mesh** - Skeletal Meshes are used usually for characters

(hu-manoid 3D objects), these are special meshes that have bone objects inside of them which allow us to perform animations on them. An animation revolves around moving these bones in the 3D space in a specified sequence. The sequence has multiple frames and can span multiple seconds depending on what we wish to do. This mesh has bones, each bone might have weight and could be attached to other bones. This mesh could be used by the player to move around the world. Critically it can be used to be modified around specific bones.

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Figure 2: Skeletal Mesh Example

- **Blueprint** - Blueprint is a piece of code that is visualized through nodes, this is a way to visually script logic inside the application.
- **Animation Blueprint** - An animation blueprint holds the logic that would animate an object: the object could be a static or a skeletal mesh. In our case we will animate a skeletal mesh.

- **Widget** - A widget is a piece (component) of the UI. It could be an interactive button, slider, etc. The point is this is an isolated and reusable component that could be applied to any UI. This component may have its own logic and it is programmable.

- **HUD** - Is a Heads Up Display, this will be our primary UI through which the user can interact with. The HUD usually has multiple wid-gets that it displays.

After knowing all these terms, this section will be split into 7 main parts:

- 3D Model Creation

- UI/UX
- Animation

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- Mathematical model for deformation
- Creation of the 3D world
- Creating the player controls
- Deployment of code to multiple platforms

3.1 3D Model Creation

In order to visualize the female body in 3D space we would first need to create its 3D representation. For this I have chosen Blender software. This is an open source software that has extensive support for modeling 3D and 2D objects. We could animate them, rig them, and export them into different file formats for later use. This software has been chosen mainly due to its quality and that it is open source. Other alternatives like ZBrush and Maya are licensed and very expensive, although they provide extra functionality Blender is used in multiple AAA productions so it will suffice for this rather simple prototype. The 3D model of the female body would not be created from scratch, there are many already created ones. We will use one of them as a baseline model to work from. This is the model used throughout the

Figure 3: 3D Model of the female body in Blender

rest of the application. In order to make it work however, I have added extra

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bones in the breast of the model and also in the pelvis area. These bones would allow for finer deformation of the mesh later on when we move to the animation.

3.2 UI/UX

The UI of the application would be developed inside Unreal Engine 5. The engine has support and capability of creating very complex UI not only the components themselves but also animating the UI. The reason for choosing this technology is due to its stability, tooling, and also it has been battle tested throughout many applications. Fortnite (one of the most popular games ever made) is built using this engine thus it only shows what is possible to be done using it. The UI would come in the form of sliders that could be used for manipulating the mesh. Each slider will have a text which would clearly describe its purpose and the slider will modify specific parts of the mesh. This makes it very intuitive for the user and easy to understand how to work with the application. Another part of the UI/UX is the position of the UI. It will be placed in the bottom center of the screen. This will allow for the user to have fast and easy access while also not compromising the field of view for the 3D objects in the scene. This is a representation of the UI as we can see each slider has its own supporting text while at the same time choosing the color scheme in such a way that the user would not get confused.

3.3 Animation

The Unreal Engine 5 provides solutions for animating Skeletal and Static Meshes. Each mesh can have its own animation blueprint that will control the logic of how the mesh will move based on certain parameters. In our case we wish to deform the female mesh based on the input value received from the sliders. In order to animate a mesh we need to first create an animation sequence that will act as the base pose from which we will animate. This sequence can be only a single frame like in our case or multiple seconds of animation that we could tap into and play with based on the frame. In our case we will be concerned with 3 parts of the mesh body:

- Left breast
- Right breast
- Pelvis (Hips)

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Figure 4: UI Design

We will start with the base pose and perform 3 bone transformations each frame based on the slider values. A transform is a data structure which holds 3 values:

- Position (3D Vector)
- Rotation (3D Vector)
- Scale (3D Vector)

Since we do not wish to change the position or rotation of the objects we will only animate the scale. This is where we will see later on the mathematical model will decide how much to exactly change the scale. The scale 3D vector has 3 components: x,y,z (for each of the axes in 3D space). These are the parameters we will modify. Below we can see implementation of this animation blueprint and how it will look.

3.4 Mathematical Model For Deformation

In order to achieve the visual effect we want we need to carefully think about the deformation algorithm that we will apply to the mesh. Each bone has

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Figure 5: Animation Blueprint logic for the breast and hips augmentation

a specific: position, rotation, scale and a hidden parameter baked into the mesh called weight. Unreal Engine uses a left-hand coordinate system. This is important since we will apply some sort of scaling on all of the 3 - axis of the bone in order to change its appearance. Although the deformation will not be perfect due to the fact that the bone transformation described above changes the bone itself but the features of the mesh not so much, so any lighting, shading, etc might still look a little ill-formed. This could be accounted for by adding multiple bones per breast in order to create a fine grain control, however for this prototype this was not needed. I came up with the following hyperparameters:

- **Slider Range** - 0.3 to 1.0
- **X Per Point** - $(1 - sF)/2 + sF$, where sF is **scaleFactor**
- **Y Per Point** - **scaleFactor**
- **Z Per Point** - **scaleFactor**

Per point means that if we move the slider by 1 unit to the left or right what type of change will each axis experience. This is by far the trickiest to get right in order to make it look and feel natural and useful. The general solution is the following: we obtain a scalar value from the slider, this slider is then passed onto the character which performs computation to update the 3 vectors which hold the scale of the: left breast, right breast, and pelvis. Then each of these vectors is fed to the animation blueprint where they update the bone transforms.

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Figure 6: OnValueChanged event, slider scalar value update logic

This event listens for changes in the UI and then updates a local class variable which stores the scalar value for the hips, left and right breast. The way we set the values in the animation blueprint after we have calculated appropriate vector parameters for each breast and the hips:

Figure 7: Character blueprint logic for augmentation or breasts and hips vectors

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The code that you see in the figure 7 executes on every tick of the game in the character blueprint. We scale the breast and the hips so that we can use the values later inside the animation blueprint.

Figure 8: Breast deformation formula

This function shown in figure 8 performs the scaling of the breast. It modifies the x,y,and z component by a scalar value obtained from the slider in order to create believable animation. After the values have been modified we create a vector that we will use for the scale, we populate it with the 3 parameters and we set the scale vector in the animation blueprint in order to use it in the next frame.

Figure 9: Breast deformation formula

The function shown in figure 9 scales the hips is just a setter. This is because we have very little movement range for the hips slider, otherwise we will observe unnatural deformation.

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3.5 Creation of 3D World

In order to create the simulation we need to create a 3D world where the simulation will be displayed in. Unreal Engine 5 has many tools that can allow us to create this world. The basic of the world will be to create an open world which has a sky, a plane with 4 surrounding walls and in the middle our 3D model of the female body. There will be some more terminology regarding this section that we need to know:

- **Light sources:**

– **Sky light** - This is a sphere object which captures light emitted from a sun and distributes it across the scene and the objects.

– **Point light** - This is a form of light source (image a light bulb) it can spread light in some radius. The light color can be chosen by us as well as many other parameters. This light source can be one of 3 types: Static (this is the best for easy of computation), Stationary (this one can have its properties changed but not position, also good computationally), and Movable (we do not use these since very heavy computation and achieve poor performance on mobile platforms)

– **Directional Light** - This acts as sunlight. The source is infinitely far away and emits light in a specified color and strength (again many other parameters could be touched but we will not concern ourselves with them).

- **Sky** - Comes in two flavors

– **Sky Sphere** - A 3D sphere which acts as the world. This creates an artificial feeling that we have a sky and it is used on mobile platforms since they could not handle actual open world settings.

– **Sky atmosphere** - Could be used to create an open world scene

- **Fog** - Exponential height fog: This is used to distribute light throughout the scene otherwise everything but the placed actors would appear to be black.

- **Clouds** - Volumetric clouds: This is the cloud that we see in the sky. They are only material used on the sphere otherwise too much compute cost will go into displaying them, again this is important for mobile platform performance.

Figure 10: 3D world

The world shown in figure 10 is a representation of our world that would be used to handle the simulation. The world is optimized for performance and includes only the essentials in order to create a believable and minimalistic environment where the user can carry out the simulation. We do not need anything more and if more things are added this would only distract the user from the true goal of the application.

3.6 Deployment of code to multiple platforms

Unreal Engine provides ways to simulate development on multiple platforms inside the engine using emulators. I have also taken into account simulating on my own devices. In order to distribute the code the engine itself provides functionality to set up different build settings. In our project we have:

- **Debug**
- **Release**
- **Distribution**

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The debug build is not optimized by the compiler and includes debug

sym-bols which allow for easy debugging when testing the application locally. The release build is meant for local testing of what the build would look like if distributed. It does not include any debug symbols and it is optimized for performance. Finally, the distribution build is meant to be actually distributed to multiple vendors such as: Google play or App Store. The engine itself allows us to enter our credentials for either of these platforms and with a click of a button to build the code and distribute it automatically to them. This workflow allows us to have not only continuous integration using tools like github, but also continuous delivery.

3.7 Important Design Decisions

From the start, I knew that the technology stack would be one of the most important design decisions. I believe that choosing such a capable technology that has proven itself in the computer graphics world was a great choice. It had all the facilities I needed in order to create this prototype fast and worry only about essential design problems in the given domain space, not on low-level stuff like how to render a vertex array, how to write shader, how to display everything on screen in 60 FPS, etc. There are many more benefits to choosing Unreal, like the Meta Humans, Meta Sounds, fastest growing 3D technology, etc all of which are crucial in order for this project to succeed at potentially a later stage. Another important design decision was to keep using the default pawn as the player object and use the woman mesh as just a character placed in the scene. This gave us a few benefits: out-of-the-box controls for the camera, detached logic from movement, and separation of concerns. This architecture design allows us to keep the logic relevant to the woman mesh inside its own blueprint, if we wish to modify the existing default pawn we can always create our own and do it, however by adhering to this separation we now have cleaner code and easier time to navigate the project. Finally, maybe the most important design decision for our problem domain was to use bones as a point for transformation. Using mesh bones instead of virtual bones (Unreal Engine specific), or index array transformation (very low level), meant that we have a portable solution in some sense. Because if we ever need to change engine versions well the woman mesh is in a proper format, we only need to change a few pieces in the code and it works. Second of all, this solution allows for much more precise bone manipulation due to knowing the weights of the bones beforehand and also having much finer control over the position, scale, and rotation of the original placement of the extra breast and pelvis bones.

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3.8 Class Diagrams

Figure 13: Dependency flow of the HUD blueprint class

Class diagrams are essential if you want to perform modern software en-gineering and adhere to the principles of CI/CD, and TDD. This allows developers to spot mistakes in their design early on and figure out better solutions before the technical debt accumulates too much. For further devel-opment of the project this would be a great source of information to check how are you design decisions influencing the code and its dependencies.

4 Project Extensibility And Improvements

There are many areas to where the project could be extended and I would in this section outline a few of them while also providing some guidance on how to navigate the project. First of all, right now the main pieces of logic reside in the: Character blueprint, UI blueprints, and the Animation blueprints. As stated, a logical next step is to create a custom character control and adapt multiple forms of control, using keyboard and mouse, joystick, fingers, and etc. This would allow the designer of the application to expose more hyperparameters for the user to edit and customize to fit his needs and make the application have a better look and feel. Another improvement that could be made is that now we run our logic on every tick of the game, ie if your phone / tablet is 120Hz then you run the logic 120 times per second, a better approach would be to use event based programming with linear interpolation for the animations to smoothen things out. Another improvement that could be made is to add more bones to each breast (I would suggest around 5 per breast), so that you could have a much better, smoother, and fine controlled transformation of the breast. This would make the calculations a little more

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complex, but nothing in the realm of impossible. As far as UI / UX

comes, it would be nice to create a main menu for the project with a nice UI, then maybe a character picker, with some customization before proceeding to the real time transformation of different parts of the body, this would give the project much more personalization. Due to the nature of this project there is inherently very little computation that should be done, there is no fluid simulation, Newtonian physics, etc, thus you could maintain the whole project using blueprints. If the performance takes a slight hit you can always nativize the blueprints via an option and then they would run nearly as fast as c++ but they would be very hard to debug. Of course if visual scripting is not the thing for you the project could easily be rewritten in c++ by an experienced programmer in maybe 2 days. As stated the room for improvements is big and once you understand the overall structure of the project, the engine and how certain things are supposed to be done then it would be fairly easy to add new functionality.